

1 **Enhanced H₂ production in the aqueous-phase reforming of maltose by**
2 **feedstock pre-hydrogenation**

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12
13 **Abstract**

14 Coupled hydrogenation and aqueous-phase reforming (APR) was studied as an approach
15 to enhance H₂ production from brewery wastewater, where maltose is the main
16 component. Hydrogenation of maltose-bearing wastewater produced essentially maltitol.
17 APR stage was performed over PtPd/C catalysts. Faster catalyst deactivation was
18 observed in the APR of maltose than in the APR of maltitol, especially at high feedstock
19 concentration. Higher H₂ selectivity and yield were achieved in the APR of maltitol. The
20 increase of temperature from 175 to 225 °C changed the reaction pathways, favouring the
21 production of C1-C2 alkanes for both feedstocks. Higher selectivity to liquid-phase
22 products was obtained in the APR of maltose, evidencing also reaction routes favouring
23 the formation of solid carbonaceous deposits that lead to higher catalyst deactivation. The
24 coupled process can be considered as efficient since H₂ production compensated for H₂
25 consumption in the hydrogenation stage and catalyst durability was increased.
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30 **Keywords:** hydrogen, aqueous-phase reforming, hydrogenation, brewery wastewater,
31 maltose
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1. Introduction

Aqueous-phase reforming (APR) is a potential route for the valorisation of organic compounds to gaseous fuels such as H_2 [1]. Important efforts have been made in the application of APR to biorefinery products and side streams [2,3]. Moreover, some studies have shown that biomass-derived organic compounds in wastewaters can also be suitable feedstocks for APR, with sugars as particularly relevant components of wastewater from food and beverage industries [4–6]. In the APR of brewery wastewater, promising results have been also achieved in terms of organic matter removal and H_2 production, with H_2 yield significantly higher than for the anaerobic digestion (12.2 mmol H_2 /g chemical oxygen demand ($COD_{initial}$) [4]. APR of cheese whey also showed a high H_2 yield, similar to that obtained in anaerobic fermentation (4 mol H_2 /mol lactose) [5]. The valorisation of waste compounds contained in wastewater is one of the strong points of this new approach, since techno-economic studies on H_2 production by APR have shown that the feedstock may contribute largely to the production costs [7].

The concentration of organic matter in wastewaters is generally lower than the biorefinery feedstocks usually considered in APR, which could have a significant influence on the catalytic performance. In the APR of brewery wastewater, at low wastewater concentration (1531 mg of $COD_{initial}$ /L) ca. 99 % of the organic matter was removed giving H_2 yield of 15.4 mmol H_2 /g $COD_{initial}$, while at higher concentration (11204 mg of $COD_{initial}$ /L) these values decreased to 51 % and 7.3 mmol H_2 /g $COD_{initial}$, respectively [4]. In the APR of sugars, a higher H_2 selectivity was observed when feedstocks with lower glucose concentrations were used [1]. This is consistent with a lower rate of side reactions to form liquid phase products, such as organic acids and aldehydes, which are less favoured at low sugar concentration [8,9]. However, the use of diluted solutions might not be economically attractive, requiring high energy input to reach the reaction

1 temperature (up to 250 °C). Nevertheless, in the case of wastewaters a higher margin for
2 operating at lower concentration of organic matter can be expected because APR would
3 be integrated in the waste management scheme, where higher energy inputs may be more
4 affordable.

5 Otherwise, the potential of sugar-based feedstocks and wastewaters in the APR can be
6 hampered by reactions involving aldehyde and ketone groups of sugars that lead to
7 catalyst deactivation [10], mostly by formation of carbonaceous deposits on the catalysts
8 surface [8]. In addition, lower H₂ yields and selectivity have been reported in the APR of
9 sugars, such as glucose, than in the APR of polyols and sugar alcohols (sorbitol, glycerol,
10 ethylene glycol) [1,9]. Therefore, a strategy to improve H₂ production in sugar-based
11 feedstocks can be a combination of hydrogenation with APR. Thus, in the hydrogenation
12 stage, sugars can be converted to more reduced compounds, which react more selectively
13 to H₂ and CO₂ in the APR stage. In this context, Davda and Dumesic [9] performed a
14 study that combined hydrogenation and APR of glucose. They observed that after
15 hydrogenation of glucose to sorbitol in a first step, a high H₂ selectivity (62.4 %) was
16 achieved and the production of H₂ was ca. 3 fold higher than for direct APR of glucose.
17 Irmak *et al.* [11] also performed hydrogenation of glucose and biomass hydrolysates
18 before APR and reported a significantly higher H₂ yield and selectivity than for non-
19 hydrogenated solutions. Godina *et al.* [12] also combined hydrogenation and APR to
20 produce hydrogen from commercial sucrose. Thus, hydrogenation of key components
21 before APR can be an alternative to reduce undesirable reactions and improve H₂
22 production. Even if some H₂ is consumed in the hydrogenation of the feedstocks, it can
23 be compensated by a higher overall net H₂ production. Likewise, hydrogenation can
24 facilitate the use of solutions with a higher concentration and diminish deactivation of the
25 catalysts.

1 This work aims to contribute to knowledge and understanding on the processability by
2 APR of diluted feedstocks based on sugars. Hydrogenation of maltose has been evaluated
3 as an approach to increase suitability of brewery wastewater as a feedstock for APR and
4 H₂ production. Maltose has been chosen as a model compound because it is the main
5 substance component, amounting for ca. 50 wt. % of the organic components in brewery
6 wastewaters, which also include sugars, soluble starch, yeast, ethanol, and volatile fatty
7 acids as other components [13,14]. On the other hand, brewery wastewater has a large
8 potential for valorisation by APR taking into account that the brewing industry generates
9 large volumes of wastewaters (3-10 L wastewater/L beer) [14] with a high organic load
10 ranging from 2000 to 32500 mg of COD/L [15].

11

12 **2. Experimental**

13 **2.1. Preparation and characterization of support and catalyst**

14 A PtPd/C catalyst was used in the APR experiments, since Pt and Pd catalysts have
15 exhibited high selectivity for H₂ production and low selectivity for alkane production
16 [16]. On the other hand, PtPd catalysts have shown to be twice more selective for H₂
17 production than Pt catalyst in the APR of glycerol, using carbon nanotubes as a support
18 [17]. The PtPd/C catalyst (2.5 wt. % Pt and 1.25 wt. % Pd) was prepared by incipient
19 wetness impregnation using PdCl₂ (Kraszvetmet, Krasnoyarsk, Russia) and H₂PtCl₆
20 (Kraszvetmet, Krasnoyarsk, Russia) as metals precursors and a mesoporous carbon
21 Sibunit, developed at the Omsk centre of new chemical chemical technologies of
22 Boreskov Institute of Catalysis, as a support. After co-impregnation of the metal
23 precursors, the catalysts were dried overnight at 110 °C, and then gently reduced starting
24 from the room temperature to 400 °C under H₂ flow (40 N mL/min) with a temperature

1 ramp 2°C/min. Thereafter, the catalyst was additionally treated with H₂ at 400 °C for 3 h
2 to remove the excess of chloride.

3 The catalyst was characterized by CO chemisorption yielding apparent metal dispersion
4 and nanoparticle mean size values of 51.6 % and 2.2 nm, respectively, for both metals.

5 The used catalysts were characterized by thermogravimetric analysis (TG) (SDT 650, TA
6 Instruments). The temperature-programmed desorption (TG-TPD) analysis was
7 performed at 450 °C for 30 min (10 °C/min heating rate) using a continuous flow of N₂
8 (50 N mL/min). Thereafter, the sample was cooled to room temperature and then the flow
9 was changed to air for the temperature-programmed oxidation (TG-TPO) which was
10 performed at 550 °C for 2 h (5 °C/min heating rate).

11 **2.2. Hydrogenation of maltose**

12 Hydrogenation of the aqueous maltose solution (2.5 wt. %) was performed in a batch
13 reactor (300 mL, Hasteloy) at 120 °C and 20 bar of H₂ [18]. In this reaction, a commercial
14 4.6 wt. % Ru catalyst supported on activated carbon was used. The details of the catalyst
15 including characterization data can be found in a previous work [19]. Maltose of 98 %
16 purity was purchased from Alfa Aesar. The maltose solution (100 mL) and the catalyst
17 (0.2 g) were loaded and the reactor was purged several times with Ar before heating up,
18 stirring (1000 rpm) and pressurizing with H₂. At the beginning of the reaction, the liquid
19 samples (2.5 mL) were taken at least every 15 min and then every 30 min until the reaction
20 was stopped after 2 h. The initial liquid feedstock and liquid samples were analysed by
21 HPLC (Aminex HPX-87H, RI detector, 45 °C, 5 mM H₂SO₄, isocratic conditions, 0.6
22 mL/min).

23 **2.3. Aqueous-phase reforming experiments**

1 The APR experiments were carried out at 175, 200 and 225 °C, 30 bar of N₂ (1 % He)
2 with 0.5 g of catalyst using a continuous fixed bed reactor equipped with temperature and
3 pressure controllers. The details on the experimental set-up can be found in previous
4 works [20,21]. The reactor was heated externally and the reaction temperature was
5 monitored using a thermocouple placed outside the stainless-steel reactor tube (520 x 6.4
6 mm) next to the position of catalyst bed. The catalyst bed consisted of a mixture of the
7 catalyst (0.5 g) and sand (3 g) placed in the middle of the reactor tube between two layers
8 of sand (3.5 g above and 4.5 below). In addition to the reduction performed during the
9 synthesis (see procedure above), the catalyst was reduced in situ during 2 h before the
10 APR experiments using a temperature of 250 °C and a H₂ flow rate of 40 N mL/min.
11 Such conditions, as confirmed by temperature programmed reduction (not shown), are
12 sufficient to reduce minor amounts of surface oxides formed in the catalyst during
13 storage.

14 The APR experiments were started at a temperature of 175 °C, which was raised to 200
15 °C after 24 h time-on-stream (TOS) and to 225 °C after additional 24 h. Aqueous solutions
16 containing 1 and 2.5 wt. % of model compounds were used in the experiments. The
17 feedstocks were fed into the reactor with a HPLC pump using 0.1 mL/min of the liquid
18 flow rate. The weight-hour space velocities (*WHSV*), calculated as mass of the substrate
19 per hour divided by the mass of catalyst, were 0.12 h⁻¹ and 0.3 h⁻¹ for 1 and 2.5 %
20 solutions, respectively. A constant N₂ flow rate 34 N mL/min containing 1 % He was
21 used to purge the reaction system, to maintain the pressure inside the reactor, and as a
22 carrier gas. The gas produced was analysed online by a Micro-Gas chromatograph
23 (Agilent Micro-GC 3000A) equipped with four columns. H₂, CO, CO₂ and C1-C7 alkanes
24 were detected in the gas produced. The initial feedstocks and the liquid effluents were

1 analysed by HPLC following the same procedure previously applied for hydrogenation
2 samples.

3 Equations 1 to 7 were used to quantify the results of experiments and define performance
4 parameters. Conversion of single compounds was calculated as Equation 1:

$$5 \text{ Conversion (\%)} = \frac{FC_{initial} - FC_{final}}{FC_{initial}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

6 where FC is the feed concentration in the initial feedstock ($FC_{initial}$) and final effluent
7 (FC_{final}) in mol/L.

8 Carbon conversion to gas (CC_{gas}) was calculated according to Equation 2:

$$9 \text{ CC}_{gas} (\%) = \frac{C_{gas}}{C_{initial}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

10 where C_{gas} is the total molar carbon flow detected in all gas phase products (CO_2 and
11 alkanes) in mol C/min and $C_{initial}$ is the molar carbon flow in the initial feedstock (mol
12 C/min).

13 The H_2 selectivity and yield were calculated by Equations (3) and (4), respectively:

$$14 \text{ Selectivity}_{H_2} (\%) = \frac{H_{2gas} \times 2}{\text{total of hydrogen in the gas phase products}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$15 \text{ Yield}_{H_2} (\%) = \frac{H_{2gas}}{H_{2stoichiometric}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

16 where H_{2gas} is the molar flow of H_2 in the gas phase (mol/min) and $H_{2stoichiometric}$ is
17 the amount of H_2 (mol/min) that would ideally be obtained from the stoichiometric
18 conversion of the feedstock to H_2 and CO_2 . The total amount of hydrogen in the gas phase
19 products was calculated as a sum of each identified product molar flow multiplied by the
20 number of hydrogen atoms in the respective molecule.

1 For selectivity to CO₂ and alkanes the Equation (5) was used:

$$2 \text{ Selectivity}_j (\%) = \frac{C_{j\text{gas}}}{C_{\text{gas}}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

3 where $C_{j\text{gas}}$ is the amount of carbon in a product j in the gas phase, in mol C/min.

4 The yield of liquid products was determined by Equation (6):

$$5 \text{ Yield}_j (\%) = \frac{C_{j\text{liq}}}{C_{\text{initial}}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

6 where $C_{j\text{liq}}$ is the amount of carbon in a product j in the liquid phase, in mol C/min.

7 Turnover frequency for H₂ production (TOF_{H_2}) was calculated taking into account
8 contribution of both metals in the following way:

$$9 \text{ TOF}_{H_2} (\text{min}^{-1}) = \frac{H_{2\text{gas}}}{MD \times m_{\text{cat}} \times \left(\frac{ML_{Pt}}{MM_{Pt}} + \frac{ML_{Pd}}{MM_{Pd}} \right)} \quad (7)$$

10 where MD is the apparent metal dispersion of both metals (Pt and Pd) obtained from CO
11 chemisorption analysis, m_{cat} is the mass of catalyst, ML_{Pt} is the Pt loading, ML_{Pd} is the
12 Pd loading, MM_{Pt} is the molar mass of Pt and MM_{Pd} is the molar mass of Pd.

13

14 **3. Results and Discussion**

15 **3.1. Hydrogenation of maltose**

16 The reaction scheme for maltose hydrogenation is represented in Figure 1. It is
17 characterized by formation of maltitol as the main product and other side products such
18 as glucose and sorbitol [18].

19

Figure 1. Scheme of maltose hydrogenation (adapted from [18])

The evolution of maltose and maltitol concentration with time during the hydrogenation experiments is showed in Figure 2. After 2 h of reaction, maltose conversion of 99.6 % was obtained, with a maltitol yield of 94.1 % (wt.). Sorbitol was also identified in the liquid phase resulting in a yield of 1.2 % (wt.) after 2 h of reaction, while glucose was not detected in the final effluent under the reaction conditions used. Traces of acids, such as acetic, formic and lactic, were also identified in the liquid phase. These acids can be formed through intermediate hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), which can be formed by glucose dehydration [22]. Finally, the carbon mass balance closure was 95.7 wt. %. These results show that quantitative hydrogenation of maltose can be achieved and that maltitol can be considered as the main component to be processed in the subsequent APR stage.

1

2 Figure 2. Concentration dependencies of maltose and maltitol with time during
 3 hydrogenation (reaction conditions: 120 °C, 20 bar of H₂, 2 h of reaction, 100 mL of 2.5
 4 % maltose solution, 0.2 g of 4.6 wt. % Ru/C catalyst, 1000 rpm)

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6 3.2. APR of maltose and maltitol

7 3.2.1. Time-on-stream behaviour

8 APR experiments were conducted using 1 and 2.5 wt. % aqueous solutions of maltitol
 9 (Alfa Aesar, 95 %). The APR of maltose was also studied at the same conditions for
 10 comparison. As indicated above, the experiments were started at 175 °C, and continued
 11 at 200 °C and 225 °C. At each temperature, a stabilization period of 1 – 6 h TOS was
 12 needed until the conversion and gas production remained stable. Experiments were
 13 performed for up to 72 h TOS without significant deactivation or increase of pressure in
 14 the reactor, for both 1 and 2.5 % maltitol (Figure 3).

1

2

3 Figure 3. Conversion and *CC gas* in APR of (a) 1 and (b) 2.5 % maltitol (reaction
 4 conditions: 30 bar, 0.5 g of PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.12$ and 0.3 h^{-1})

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6 In the APR experiments with maltose solutions (Figure 4), the catalyst showed a
 7 significant deactivation after 48 h TOS. Deactivation was more evident when the
 8 temperature was raised to 225 °C, even for maltose concentration of 1 %. Likewise, a
 9 significant increase in the reactor pressure was observed after 56 h TOS in the case of
 10 experiments with 2.5 % maltose, and after 60 h TOS in the case of experiments with 1 %
 11 maltose. The rise in pressure may be ascribed to the formation of carbonaceous deposits

1 inside the reactor and could also be responsible for deactivation observed earlier [9]. The
 2 side reactions would be less favoured in the APR of maltitol, which is typical for polyols
 3 in comparison to sugars. In addition, these side reactions seem to be favoured at higher
 4 temperatures and for more concentrated feedstock solutions, since the experiment with
 5 2.5 % maltose at 225 °C could only be carried out during 8 h TOS, while with 1 % maltose
 6 at the same temperature an increase of pressure happened after 12 h TOS.

9 Figure 4. Conversion and *CC gas* in APR of (a) 1 and (b) 2.5 % maltose (reaction
 10 conditions: 30 bar, 0.5 g of PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.12$ and 0.3 h^{-1})

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3.2.2. Catalytic performance

The performance parameters for the APR of maltose and maltitol after catalyst stabilization (average of the stable period) are discussed below. For the APR of maltose at 225 °C, where some deactivation was observed, the results are given as average values within the TOS tested. Conversion of the initial feedstock at different temperatures is shown in Figure 5. As can be seen, APR of maltose led to higher conversion values than APR of maltitol, especially at lower temperatures. In addition, the conversion values increased with increasing temperature and decreased with increasing concentration of the initial feedstock. Pipitone *et al.* [2] also reported that the conversion of glucose and xylose in APR was significantly higher than the conversion of sorbitol and xylitol at 230-270 °C, and that differences were more evident at high temperature. Thus, at 175 °C and using 1 % maltitol, the conversion was 18.4 % and this value decreased to 8.3 % using 2.5 % maltitol. At the same temperature, the conversion of maltose was 86.4 and 38.2 % using an initial concentration of 1 and 2.5 %, respectively. When the temperature was increased to 225 °C, both substrates showed very high conversion values, well above 94.5 %.

16

17 Figure 5. Conversion of maltose and maltitol in APR at different temperatures and initial
18 concentration (reaction conditions: 30 bar, 0.5 g of PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.12$ and 0.3
19 h^{-1})

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Figure 6 shows the *CC gas* at different temperatures. The lowest concentration solutions and the highest reaction temperatures led to the highest *CC gas* values. Moreover, APR of maltose showed higher *CC gas* values than APR of maltitol, consistent with higher conversion values achieved for maltose. Therefore, the highest *CC gas* (79.1 %) was obtained in the APR at 225 °C of 1 % maltose.

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Figure 6. *CC gas* in the APR of maltose and maltitol at different temperatures and initial concentration (reaction conditions: 30 bar, 0.5 g of PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.12$ and 0.3 h^{-1})

13 Figure 7 shows selectivity to H_2 , CO_2 and alkanes at different temperatures. The
14 selectivity to alkanes was calculated considering all identified hydrocarbons, i.e. CH_4 ,
15 C_2H_6 , C_3H_8 , $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_{10}$, $\text{iso-C}_4\text{H}_{10}$, $n\text{-C}_5\text{H}_{12}$, $\text{iso-C}_5\text{H}_{12}$, $\text{neo-C}_5\text{H}_{12}$, $n\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{14}$, $\text{iso-C}_6\text{H}_{14}$,
16 C_6H_{12} and $n\text{-C}_7\text{H}_{16}$. APR of maltose was more selective to alkanes than APR of maltitol.
17 Selectivity to alkanes in the reactions with maltose varied from 23.5 to 37.7 %, being
18 between 14.9 and 23.2 % for the reactions with maltitol. Accordingly, selectivity to H_2

1 was higher in the APR of maltitol (68.7 – 84.2 %) than in the APR of maltose (30.3 –
2 64.0 %). Davda and Dumesic [9] also reported that H₂ selectivity increased from 13.4 to
3 62.4 % and alkanes selectivity decreased from 47.5 to 21.3 % by combining
4 hydrogenation and APR of glucose, where the main hydrogenation product was sorbitol.
5 Pipitone *et al.* [2] also observed that APR of sorbitol and xylitol was more selective for
6 H₂ production than APR of glucose and xylose, while Irmak *et al.* [11] reported that in
7 the APR of glucose and biomass hydrolysate the more reduced feedstocks produced
8 significantly higher H₂ selectivity and yield than the non-reduced forms.

9 In the APR of both maltose and maltitol the H₂ selectivity decreased when the solution
10 concentration increased from 1 to 2.5 %, although this effect was more pronounced in the
11 case of maltose, probably due to a higher contribution of undesired side reactions to form
12 liquids products and carbonaceous deposits [9]. This decrease in H₂ selectivity was
13 followed by an increase in alkanes selectivity, which was more pronounced at the highest
14 temperature.

1

2 Figure 7. H₂, CO₂ and alkanes selectivity in APR of (a) 1 % maltose, (b) 1 % maltitol, (c)
 3 2.5 % maltose and (d) 2.5 % maltitol at different temperatures (reaction conditions: 30
 4 bar, 0.5 g of PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.12$ and 0.3 h^{-1})

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6 A more detailed speciation of alkanes is provided in Figure 8, where the identified
 7 hydrocarbons were grouped according to the chain length, from C1 to C7. APR of maltose
 8 at 175 °C was mainly selective to C5, achieving up to 24.3 % of selectivity to this alkane
 9 when a 2.5 % initial concentration was used (Figure 8 (c)). The C5 selectivity
 10 significantly decreased with increasing temperature and at 225 °C the selectivity to C5
 11 reached a maximum of 1.3 % (Figure 8 (a) and (c)). The APR of maltitol also showed a
 12 maximum of C5 selectivity at 175 °C, although the values were significantly lower than
 13 for the APR of maltose (Figure 8 (b) and (d)). C5 alkanes could be formed from
 14 consecutive dehydration/hydrogenation and/or dehydrogenation/decarbonylation steps of
 15 intermediate compounds present in the liquid phase with C5-C6 atoms [7]. The increase

1 in temperature and initial feedstock conversion favoured selectivity to short chain alkanes
2 for both maltose and maltitol, and at 225 °C the APR of maltose was more selective to C2
3 while the APR of maltitol was more selective to C1. In addition, at all the studies
4 temperatures, the initial feedstock concentration and conversion, the APR of maltitol was
5 more selective to C1 than to other alkanes. These results indicate that the increase of the
6 temperature and the use of more reduced compounds changed the reaction pathways,
7 favouring the fragmentation of the initial feedstock through C-C and C-O bond cleavages
8 [23], producing short chain alkanes. Similar global alkanes selectivity was observed in
9 the APR of xylitol using PtRe/C catalyst, although the selectivity to a particular alkane
10 displayed large variations with the metallic active phase used [20]. On the other hand, in
11 the APR of sorbitol, a high selectivity to C1 and C2 alkanes was observed using PtPd/C
12 catalyst [24]. A higher alkanes selectivity was also achieved for monometallic Pd
13 catalysts than for Pt catalysts [25]

1

2 Figure 8. Selectivity towards C1 to C7 alkanes at different temperatures in APR of (a) 1
 3 % maltose, (b) 1 % maltitol, (c) 2.5 % maltose and (d) 2.5 % maltitol. Numbers in brackets
 4 indicate conversion in the experiments at different temperatures (reaction conditions: 30
 5 bar, 0.5 g of PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.12$ and 0.3 h^{-1})

6

7 Figure 9 (a) shows the yield to H_2 while Figure 9 (b) displays the turnover frequency for
 8 H_2 production (TOF_{H_2}) at different temperatures. Both H_2 yield and TOF_{H_2} increased
 9 with reaction temperature and when less concentrated solutions were used. Under all
 10 tested operating conditions, the APR of maltitol always led to a higher H_2 yield and TOF_{H_2}
 11 H_2 than the APR of maltose. In a former study on APR of glucose [9], the net production
 12 of H_2 per mol of glucose was improved almost 3 fold by addition of a hydrogenation stage
 13 before reforming leading to sorbitol. In the current work, the H_2 production was maximum
 14 for a reaction temperature of 225 °C and initial feedstock concentration of 1 %, resulting
 15 in a H_2 yield and TOF_{H_2} for maltose of 26.4 % and 0.29 min^{-1} , respectively, while in the

1 APR of maltitol these values increased to 36.6 % and 0.42 min^{-1} . Other authors found
2 similar values of $TOF H_2$ in APR of polyols from glucose degradation (sorbitol, glycerol
3 and ethylene glycol) using Pt/ Al_2O_3 catalyst ($0.4\text{-}0.9 \text{ min}^{-1}$) [26].

4

5 Figure 9. (a) H_2 yield and (b) $TOF H_2$ in the APR of maltose and maltitol at different
6 temperatures and initial feedstock concentration (reaction conditions: 30 bar, 0.5 g of
7 PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.12$ and 0.3 h^{-1})

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9 Arrhenius representations of the reaction rate for APR of 2.5 % maltose and maltitol,
10 expressed as $TOF H_2$, are shown in Figure 10. The apparent activation energies were 108
11 kJ/mol for APR of maltose and 61 kJ/mol for APR of maltitol. Comparison with the
12 literature is not straightforward because no results have been reported so far for maltose
13 and maltitol. However, the values are within the range of apparent activation energy found
14 in the literature for the APR of glycerol (20 – 67 kJ/mol), methanol (140 kJ/mol) and
15 ethylene glycol (100 kJ/mol) [27,28].

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2 Figure 10. Arrhenius plot for APR of maltose and maltitol (reaction conditions: 30 bar,
3 2.5 % initial concentration, 0.5 g of PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.3 \text{ h}^{-1}$)

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5 Finally, in order to compare the catalytic performance in the APR of maltose and maltitol
6 at similar conversion values, an additional experiment was performed at 200 °C using 2.5
7 % maltitol and $WHSV$ of 0.105 h^{-1} (0.5 g of catalyst and 0.035 mL/min of flow rate). Table
8 1 shows the obtained results, also including for comparison the results for APR of maltose
9 at the same temperature, initial solution concentration and $WHSV$ of 0.3 h^{-1} . At a similar
10 conversion level (74 – 80 %), the APR of maltitol yielded higher CC gas than APR of
11 maltose. In addition, as observed previously, APR of maltose was more selective to
12 alkanes production than APR of maltitol, while the selectivity to H_2 was significantly
13 higher in the APR of maltitol. Regarding the selectivity to C1-C7 alkanes, APR of maltitol
14 was more selective to light alkanes, C1-C3 alkanes represented 75 % of the total alkanes
15 selectivity, while APR of maltose was more selective to C4-C7 (53 % of the total alkanes
16 selectivity). Furthermore, the selectivity to C1 was twice as high in the APR of maltitol
17 than in the APR of maltose, whereas the selectivity to C7 was 17 times higher in the APR

1 of maltose. This high selectivity to C7 is indicative of the occurrence of condensation
 2 reactions [29], as otherwise C6 can be considered as the longest chain alkanes formed by
 3 dehydration/hydrogenation and/or dehydrogenation/decarbonylation [7]. The H₂ yield
 4 and *TOF H₂* were also higher in the APR of maltitol, highlighting that under these
 5 conditions the H₂ yield increased from 3.4 to 12.4 %, evidencing the potential impact of
 6 a hydrogenation stage before APR.

7

8 Table 1. Results from APR of maltose and maltitol at similar conversion levels: 80.5 and
 9 74.3 % correspondingly (200 °C, 2.5 % initial concentration, *WHSV* = 0.3 h⁻¹ maltose and
 10 0.105 h⁻¹ maltitol)

	Maltose	Maltitol
Conversion (%)	80.5	74.3
CC gas (%)	15.5	24.5
H₂ selectivity (%)	53.2	71.7
CO₂ selectivity (%)	72.7	76.1
Alkanes selectivity (%)	27.3	23.9
Selectivity (%)		
C1	6.3	12.2
C2	4.4	5.1
C3	2.1	0.7
C4	1.0	0.5
C5	2.4	4.3
C6	4.3	0.7
C7	6.8	0.4
H₂ yield (%)	3.4	12.4
<i>TOF H₂</i> (min⁻¹)	0.10	0.12

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13 3.2.3. *Liquid phase composition*

14 The liquid phase resulting from APR at different temperatures was analysed by HPLC to
 15 identify the main reaction products and to obtain insight into the reaction mechanism.
 16 Figure 11 shows the HPLC chromatograms for reactions at 175 °C, 200 °C and 225 °C.
 17 Zoomed inserts in the Figure 11 (b), (c) and (d) illustrate the ratio between major and
 18 minor peaks. The compounds identified are similar to those observed in the liquid phase

1 of APR of other feedstocks such as sorbitol, galactitol, glycerol or xylitol [23,29–31] and
2 in the degradation of carbohydrates at high temperatures [32–34].

3 The chromatograms in Figure 11 show significantly different patterns for maltose and
4 maltitol. In the APR of maltose, glucose (3) and fructose (5) were identified, especially
5 at 175 °C. The occurrence of glucose can be ascribed to hydrolysis of maltose in the acidic
6 medium or on acidic sites of the catalyst [35], while fructose can result from isomerization
7 of glucose, which is promoted by the presence of Pt catalyst and H₂ [36]. In the APR of
8 maltitol, sorbitol (7) was identified, especially at 225 °C, whereas glucose (3) and fructose
9 (5) were not detected. Sorbitol can be produced by hydrolysis of maltitol [18] and
10 hydrogenation of glucose and fructose [37], thus a high peak observed for sorbitol at a
11 high temperature reaction (225 °C) is consistent with the decrease in H₂ selectivity
12 observed in the APR of maltitol at this temperature. On the other hand, the route of
13 hydrogenation of glucose and fructose does not seem to be favoured in the APR of
14 maltose, since sorbitol was not detected in the liquid phase for this substrate.

15 In addition to the sugars/sugar alcohols, a number of aldehydes, organic acids and
16 alcohols were identified in the APR of both maltose and maltitol, while glycolaldehyde
17 (11), propylene glycol (19) and methanol (22) were only detected in the APR of maltitol
18 and pyruvaldehyde (10), formic acid (15) and levulinic acid (18) were only detected in
19 the APR of maltose. In addition, HMF (not shown, 35.5 min) was also only detected in
20 the APR of maltose at 200 °C.

21 Regarding the distribution of the liquid products, the concentration of the compounds
22 detected are included in Supplementary Material (Table S1 and S2). In the APR of
23 maltose at 175 °C, glucose (3), formic acid (15), hydroxyacetone (20) and ethanol (24)
24 yielded the main concentrations, representing between 12.7 and 21.3 % of the starting
25 carbon. At 200 °C and using 1 % maltose, hydroxyacetone (20) and ethanol (24) obtained

1 the highest concentrations, representing 22.6 % of the starting carbon, while using 2.5 %
2 initial solution, the main concentrations correspond to glucose (3) and ethanol (24), with
3 14.1 % of the starting carbon. On the other hand, at 225 °C, the APR of maltose yielded
4 mainly ethanol (24), representing between 1.1 and 1.9 % of the starting carbon. It is
5 important to note that the high concentrations of ethanol observed at higher reaction
6 temperatures are consistent with the increase in selectivity to C2 observed above.

7 In the APR of maltitol at 175 and 200 °C, the main compounds are glyceraldehyde (8),
8 hydroxyacetone (20) and methanol (22), representing between 2.6 and 4 % of the starting
9 carbon. At 225 °C and using 1% maltitol, acetaldehyde (21), methanol (22) and ethanol
10 (24) yielded the main concentrations, representing 13.8 % of the starting carbon, while
11 using 2.5 % maltitol, sorbitol (7) was the main compound produced, with 29.3 % of the
12 starting carbon, followed by hydroxyacetone (20), with 11.4 % of the starting carbon. The
13 high concentration of hydroxyacetone and acetaldehyde observed are related to the high
14 selectivity to C1 observed in the APR of maltitol [30].

15 Regarding the influence of reaction temperature, C-C and C-O bond cleavage are
16 favoured by increasing the reaction temperature [23], leading to products with less carbon
17 atoms in the liquid phase and higher *CC gas*. In this sense, a higher concentration of
18 hydroxyacetone (20), acetaldehyde (21) and ethanol (24) was observed at 200 and 225
19 °C, also in agreement with the increase in the selectivity to C1-C2 alkanes [30]

20 Taking into account the obtained results, the degradation of maltose may proceed mainly
21 *via* hydrolysis generating glucose, which in turn leads to HMF by dehydration, becoming
22 a precursor of formic and levulinic acids [38]. This route also generates compounds that
23 could be related to the production of C5 alkanes, such as pentanol and 1,5-pentanediol
24 [5], consistent with the higher C5 selectivity observed in the APR of maltose. On the
25 other hand, degradation route of maltitol may proceed mainly *via* hydrolysis generating

1 sorbitol and glucose [18]. Sorbitol undergoes reforming to produce H_2 that also is used in
2 sequential dehydration-hydrogenation steps which together with decarbonylation
3 reactions, leading to ketones, aldehydes, acids and alcohols and then alkanes [9]. In this
4 context, Kirilin et al. [23] found that the selectivity to light alkanes (C1-C3) was higher
5 than C4-C6 alkanes in the APR of sorbitol at the same *WHSV*, consistent with high
6 selectivities to C1-C2 alkanes observed in the APR of maltitol. Other possible parallel
7 routes could be the retro-aldol fragmentation of glucose and/or fructose [5]. These routes
8 could also occur because they lead to the formation of various liquid compounds
9 identified in this work, such as glycolaldehyde, glyceraldehyde, acetaldehyde,
10 hydroxyacetone, ethanol and methanol.

11 Finally, some of the liquid phase compounds that were detected only in the APR of
12 maltose (glucose, fructose, pyruvaldehyde, HMF) are known to be relevant precursors in
13 solid humins formation during the catalytic hydrothermal conversion of carbohydrates
14 [39]. This contribution may be much lower in the APR of maltitol, where a different
15 pattern in liquid phase products distribution was found, evidencing differences in the
16 degradation routes.

1

2 Figure 11. HPLC chromatograms of the liquid samples during APR of maltose and
 3 maltitol at different temperatures and initial feedstock concentrations. Identified
 4 compounds: (1) maltose, (2) maltitol, (3) glucose, (4) xylose, (5) fructose, (6) mannitol,
 5 (7) sorbitol, (8) glyceraldehyde, (9) erythritol, (10) pyruvaldehyde, (11) glycolaldehyde,
 6 (12) glycolic acid, (13) lactic acid, (14) formaldehyde, (15) formic acid, (16) acetic acid,
 7 (17) ethylene glycol, (18) levulinic acid, (19) propylene glycol, (20) hydroxyacetone, (21)

1 acetaldehyde, (22) methanol, (23) 1-2 butanediol, (24) ethanol, (25) butyric acid and (26)
 2 isopropanol (reaction conditions: 30 bar, 0.5 g of PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.12$ and 0.3
 3 h^{-1})

4
 5 The comparative data obtained in the APR of maltose and maltitol at similar conversion
 6 levels revealed significant differences in the composition of the liquid phase, with higher
 7 yield to sugars, sugar alcohols, alcohols, acids, aldehydes and ketones, and occurrence of
 8 HMF in the APR of maltose (Table 2). Accordingly, the total carbon present in the liquid
 9 phase was higher in the APR of maltose.

10

11 Table 2. Yields of the liquid phase products obtained during APR of maltose and maltitol
 12 (200 °C, 2.5 % initial concentration, $WHSV = 0.3 h^{-1}$ maltose and $0.105 h^{-1}$ maltitol)

	Maltose	Maltitol
Conversion (%)	80.5	74.3
Yield to product (%)		
sugar/sugar alcohol		
glucose	10.2	-
xylose	0.5	0.3
fructose	4.7	-
sorbitol	-	0.6
erythritol	1.0	<0.1
alcohols		
ethylene glycol	0.5	0.2
propylene glycol	-	<0.1
methanol	-	0.6
1-2 butanediol	1.0	1.0
ethanol	3.9	2.5
isopropanol	1.2	0.1
acids		
glycolic acid	2.1	0.2
lactic acid	-	0.7
acetic acid	0.2	0.2
levulinic acid	2.2	-
butyric acid	1.6	0.2
aldehydes/ketones		
glyceraldehyde	2.9	2.3
pyruvaldehyde	0.6	-
formaldehyde	1.1	<0.1
hydroxyacetone	3.9	0.8
acetaldehyde	-	2.4
furans		

HMF	0.4	-
Total yield to identified products	38.0	12.2
Total carbon in liquid phase (%)*	57.4	37.9

*: calculated from identified products, carbon in the initial feedstock

2

3 3.2.4. Carbon Balance

4 The carbon mass balance closure was higher in the maltitol APR experiments (91 to 100
5 %) than for those with maltose (56 to 95 %). In addition, a higher carbon imbalance was
6 observed for high reaction temperatures with a higher feedstock concentration, especially
7 in the case of APR experiments with maltose, where 44 % of carbon was not detected
8 either in the liquid phase or in the gas phase. In the literature [2], the solid phase
9 production was found to increase with the initial concentration of the feedstock in APR
10 of glucose and xylose, which was attributed to formation of high molecular weight
11 compounds by condensation reactions. Therefore, deposition of the solid phase mater is
12 consistent with the lower mass balance closure for APR of maltose.

13 Considering that the undetected carbon is present in the reaction as solid phase carbon
14 species, diagrams of the carbon distribution between gas, liquid and solid phases in the
15 APR experiments are shown in Figure 12. It can be seen from these diagrams that the
16 estimated fraction of carbon in the solid phase is higher in the APR of maltose compared
17 with maltitol, even at the same feedstock conversion, and that deposition of the solid
18 carbon can be responsible for faster deactivation and collapse of the flow due to a high
19 pressure drop. It can be also observed that, in the APR of maltose, the increase of solid
20 phase formation occurs at the expense of liquid phase species formation to a higher extent
21 than in the APR of maltitol.

1

2 Figure 12. Carbon distribution in APR of (a) 1 % maltose, (b) 1 % maltitol, (c) 2.5 %
 3 maltose and (d) 2.5 % maltitol (reaction conditions: 175, 200 and 225 °C, 30 bar, 0.5 g of
 4 PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.12$ and 0.3 h^{-1})

5

6 In order to evaluate formation of the solid phase carbon species during APR experiments,
 7 the used catalysts were subjected to TG-TPD/TPO tests. Figure 13 shows the weight-loss
 8 TG-TPD/TPO profiles and the corresponding differential curves (DTG) for the PtPd/C
 9 catalyst used in the APR of 1 % maltose and maltitol and 2.5 % maltose. The quantitative
 10 values of the weight loss vary summarized in Table 3.

11 The initial peak at ca. 100 °C in TG-TPD curves can be ascribed to the loss of water. After
 12 that, the used catalysts, especially the one employed in the case of 2.5% maltose, showed
 13 a peak extending from 200 to 425 °C, which can be attributed to the loss of carbon-rich
 14 (coke-like) species or reactants/products physically adsorbed on the catalyst. The

1 percentage of the weight loss in the TG-TPD was 2.4 % in the case of the catalyst used
 2 in APR of 1% maltitol, and increased to 4.7 and 10.4 % for the APR of 1 % and 2.5 %
 3 maltose, respectively (Table 3). Therefore, during the APR of maltose higher amounts of
 4 carbon-rich species are deposited on the catalyst, and their desorption and evolution under
 5 pyrolysis lead to a higher loss weight in TG-TPR tests. Regarding the TG-TPO profiles,
 6 the displacement of the main peak towards higher combustion temperatures suggest a
 7 higher degree of structure development for the carbon-rich species deposited during upon
 8 APR of maltose. It should be also noted that TG-TPO tests are carried out subsequently
 9 to TG-TPD ones, then part of the mass oxidized during TPO can be ascribed to the
 10 carbonizate resulting from the pyrolysis of carbon-rich species during TPD. Therefore,
 11 the results obtained allow considering formation of the solid phase carbon species as a
 12 reason of catalyst deactivation observed in the APR of maltose compared to maltitol.

13

14

15 Figure 13. (a) TG-TPD and (b) TG-TPO profiles and the corresponding derivative curves
 16 of the spent PtPd/C catalysts (reaction conditions: 175, 200 and 225 °C, 30 bar, 0.5 g of
 17 PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.12$ and 0.3 h^{-1})

18

1 Table 3. Quantitative weight losses upon TG-TPD/TPO of used catalysts (reaction
 2 conditions: 175, 200 and 225 °C, 30 bar, 0.5 g of PtPd/C catalyst, $WHSV = 0.12$ and 0.3
 3 h^{-1})

Catalyst	TG-TPD (%)	TG-TPO (%)
Used in APR of 1 % Maltitol	2.4	84.9
Used in APR of 1 % Maltose	4.7	85.0
Used in APR of 2.5 % Maltose	10.4	81.8

4

5

6 3.2.5. Process efficiency

7 Regarding efficiency of the overall coupled hydrogenation and APR process, it has to be
 8 considered that 1 mol of H_2 is utilized to hydrogenate 1 mol of maltose to maltitol
 9 (Equation 8). On the other hand, considering the global APR reactions in Equations 9 and
 10 10, the maximum H_2 production from 1 mol maltose and maltitol is 24 and 25 mol,
 11 respectively. Therefore, the coupled process could be considered efficient if leads to a
 12 more stable conditions for PtPd/C catalyst performance despite a certain amount of H_2
 13 needed in the hydrogenation step.

17 As mentioned above, because the apparent activation energy for H_2 production is lower
 18 in the APR of maltitol than in the APR of maltose, selectivity for H_2 production was
 19 higher, ultimately increasing H_2 yield in the coupled process. At 225 °C the APR of 1 %
 20 maltose generated 6.3 mol of H_2 per mol of maltose, while 9.2 mol of H_2 was produced
 21 in the APR of maltitol. Thus, introduction of a hydrogenation stage before APR generated
 22 3 additional moles of H_2 than direct reforming of maltose. Therefore, the overall process
 23 could be considered efficient under these conditions. For 2.5 % feedstock the production

1 of H₂ from maltose and maltitol was 2.5 and 2.9 mol per mol of the feedstock,
2 respectively, not covering the needs for hydrogenation. At the same time, hydrogenation
3 to maltitol had a clear impact on catalyst durability, contributing to the efficiency and
4 feasibility of the process. In the view of these results, an alternative approach could
5 hydrogenation of maltose to such products as sorbitol [40,41], which can result in a higher
6 H₂ yield in subsequent APR [9,31]. The results also show a potential of APR of the diluted
7 feedstock in terms of a high conversion of substrate and selectivity to H₂.

8

9 **4. Conclusions**

10 Hydrogenation of maltose to maltitol was performed as a pre-stage of APR to increase
11 overall H₂ production and diminish the deactivation by formation of carbonaceous
12 deposits. Maltose was selected as a model compound because it is the main component
13 present in brewery wastewaters, which has a large potential for valorisation.

14 In the APR of maltose after 48 h TOS and at 225 °C, a significant catalyst deactivation
15 and increase of the pressure in the reactor was observed, probably due to formation of
16 carbonaceous deposits on the catalyst surface and on the walls of the reactor. In contrast,
17 in the APR of maltitol lower deactivation was observed, indicating that undesirable
18 reactions that take place in the liquid phase to form carbonaceous deposits are less
19 favoured. High feedstock concentration also contributed to deactivation, particularly at a
20 high reaction temperature.

21 Conversion of the initial feedstock and carbon conversion to gas phase were higher in the
22 APR of maltose, however, higher H₂ selectivity was achieved in the combined
23 hydrogenation and APR. In addition, conversion of the substrate and H₂ selectivity were

1 significantly higher at a low feedstock concentration, showing the potential of diluted
2 streams and wastewaters.

3 APR of maltose was more selective to alkanes than APR of maltitol, and both feedstocks
4 led to a remarkably high selectivity to C5 at 175 °C. At 225 °C the APR of maltose was
5 more selective to C2 while the APR of maltitol was more selective to C1. In the liquid
6 phase, higher yields of sugar, sugar alcohols, alcohols, acids, aldehydes and ketones were
7 obtained in the APR of maltose. Both H₂ yield and *TOF H₂* were higher for a high reaction
8 temperature and less concentrated feedstocks. In addition, the APR of maltitol always led
9 to a higher H₂ yield and *TOF H₂* than the APR of maltose, and the value of apparent
10 activation energy calculated was lower for APR of maltitol (61 kJ/mol) than in the APR
11 of maltose (108 kJ/mol).

12 Finally, the overall process (combined hydrogenation and APR) can be considered as
13 efficient because an increase in H₂ production compensated for the consumption in
14 hydrogenation, and moreover durability of the catalyst was increased in the APR of
15 maltitol.

16

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